

Fake Job Posting Analysis using Machine Learning

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Abstract- In recent years, there has been a great increase in the number of online job portals. However, some of the jobs being posted on these job portals are fraud and can lead to the theft of confidential data and personal information. So, fake job posting analysis is going to be a great concern for all. Thus by performing an exploratory data analysis on a pool of job that include both actual and phoney jobs, it is simple to identify these bogus job posts. It is possible to identify fake jobs and tell them apart from actual jobs using a variety of machine learning methods. This study also discusses the tasks of data cleansing, pre-processing and analysis. Finally, Support Vector Machine and Random Forest methods are applied to cleaned and preprocessed data to find the accuracy and precision. These classification models are then compared to find the classification algorithm with the highest accuracy and precision.

Keywords: Fake job, Support Vector Machine, Random Forest

I.INTRODUCTION

The pandemic crisis, economic difficulties, and coronavirus effects have significantly decreased the availability of work and led to job loss. In recent days, many companies have decided to post their job offers in websites so that it can be easily available to the job-seekers. Users can broaden their employment searches and find the best applicants by using online recruitment. This enables them to connect with qualified people across the world. So, many people started to depend on these online job portals for their job search. Online hiring has the advantage of being more affordable in terms of communication..

However, when the popularity of online recruitment increases, many scammers took this as an opportunity to use this for illegal purposes. This could be a scam by fraud people to obtain personal information and money by posting false job openings. Job-seekers easily get convinced by these offers and they become willing to provide whatever information they needed. The victim's information is combined by cyber criminals, and they either sell it on the dark web or continue to use it years later. This scam also lead to decrease the reliability and reputation of job portals. So, it has also become a major concern for admin of job portals to prevent fraud or fake jobs being posted on their portals.

In order to accomplish this, a machine learning approach is used, which makes use of a number of classification algorithms. Data theft can be stopped by identifying these bogus jobs and using the right machine learning algorithms in conjunction with the right dataset, analysis, and cleaning.. In this instance, a classification tool separates the fraudulent job postings from a broader collection of job postings.

II.LITERATURE SURVEY

There are numerous publications on detecting phoney jobs and on related subjects such as detection of spam emails and false news. These publications mostly make use of machine learning algorithms. Some of them are:

o *Spam Review Detection*

Spam review detection is used by product manufacturers and product owners to create a summary of the products and services they offer based on the reviews submitted by the customers.

o *Spam Email Detection*

E-mail spam, also known as junk e-mail, is unsolicited messages sent in bulk via e-mail. Junk email detection can help prevent spam messages from creeping into your users' inboxes and improve the user experience. Gmail, Yahoo, and Outlook used spam filtering based on Neural Networks.

o *Fake News Detetction*

The task of determining whether news is real or phoney is frequently referred to as fake news detection, which is a subtask of text categorization. False or deceptive news materials is referred to as "fake news." It is meant to trick or mislead people. There are many different types of fake news, such as clickbait, disinformation, misinformation, hoaxes, parodies, satire, rumours, misleading news, and other types that have been covered in the literature..

III.METHODOLOGY

o *Support Vector Machine*

Supervised learning model called Support Vector Machines (SVMs) can be applied to handle problems like classification and regression. They are helpful in a variety of circumstances and can handle both linear and nonlinear issues. The underlying idea of Support Vector is simple: For instance, the approach draws a line between the classes. The objective is to maximize the distance between points on either side of what is called the decision line. After separation, the model can easily guess the target class for the new case. This is the advantage of this method.

o *Random Forest*

The ensemble method enables a variety of machine learning algorithms to collaborate and enhance system accuracy. An ensemble learning strategy and a regression technique are both employed by random forest to handle classification problems.

Random Forest is a classifier that averages the results of several decision trees used on various subsets of a dataset to improve the projected accuracy of the dataset. A meta estimator called a random forest fits a number of decision

tree classifiers together. On different sub-samples of the dataset, averaging is utilized to improve forecast accuracy and control over-fitting. The sub-sample size is constrained if the max samples argument is true; otherwise, each tree is constructed using the complete dataset. This classifier includes a number of tree-like classifiers, each of which evaluates a different subsample of the dataset and selects the input class that is the most appropriate.

IV. IMPLEMENTATION

The major objective of this system is to determine whether a job posted is legitimate or not. If fake job posts are found and removed, job hunters will be free to concentrate only on real job openings. Here, we plan to import a Kaggle dataset in this system that includes details about the job, such as job id, title, location, and department. Next comes data analysis, data cleaning, and data preprocessing tasks which focuses on eliminating items like null spaces, null entries, stopwords, and so on. The data is preprocessed and cleaned to make it prediction ready before being given to the classifier for predictions.

A. Data Collection

To identify the fraudulent jobs, we trained and tested a model using data from Kaggle and the University of Aegon. We have gathered textual and numerical data in 17 columns and around 18000 rows, for the purpose of testing and training machine learning algorithms. These columns refer to the titles and information included in various job postings on websites that help people find jobs, including internshala, naukri, etc. These statistics provide a clear picture of how job is posted online. Figure 1 shows the different columns present in the dataset.

Fig.1

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M	N	O	P	Q	R	
1	job_id	title	location	department	salary_range	company_profile	description	requirements	benefits	telecommuting	has_company_logo	has_questions	employment_type	required_experience	required_education	industry	function	fraudulent
2	Marketing	US, NY, Marketing				Wife's Roadside, perfo	2, a Experience with content	0	1	0	Other	internship	Marketing	Customer	0			
3	Customer Sr	NZ, And Success				90 Seconds, the o	Organised - What we espe	What you	0	1	0	Full-time	Not Applicable	Marketing	Customer	0		
4	Commission US	IA, Weiner				Value Services pro	Our client, Implement pre-commissi	0	1	0								
5	Account Exec	US, DC, VSales				Our passion for in	THE COMP-EDUCATION & Our cultu	0	1	0	Full-time	Mid-Senior Bachelor's	Computer Sales					
6	Bill Review	US, FL, Fort Worth				SpotSource Jobst	JOB TITLE: QUALIFICATIO Full Benef	0	1	1	Full-time	Mid-Senior Bachelor's	Hospital & Health Car					
7	Accounting	US, MD,				Job Overview	Open in an environment	0	0	0								
8	Head of Cor	DE, BE, B ANDRO	DP1120000-28000			Founded in 2009,	Your Respo Your know Ho	Your Bens	0	1	1	Full-time	Mid-Senior Master's	C Online Me	Management			
9	Lead Guest	US, CA, San Francisco				AdrennyR™, miss	Who is Are Experience with	Comperit	0	1								
10	SR IBM	IBM US, FL, Pensacola				Solutions is a we	Implement MUST BE A US CITIZE	0	1	1	Full-time	Associate	Information Techno					
11	Customer Sr	US, AZ, Phoenix				Novlix Enterprise	The Custom Minimum Requirements:	0	1	0	Part-time	Entry level High School	Financial S	Customer				
12	ASP.NET Dev	US, NJ, Jersey City				100000-120000	Position: # Position: #UR	Benefits:	0	0	0	Full-time	Mid-Senior Bachelor's	Informatic	Informatic			
13	Talent Sourc	GB, LND, HR					Want to build a 2	Transfer/We Work™	re look You will j	0	1	0						
14	Applications	US, CT, Stamford				Novlix Enterprise	The Applic Requirements: 48"	5" ye	0	1	1	Full-time	Associate	Bachelor's	Management	Informatic		
15	Installers	US, FL, Orlando				Growing event pr	Event Invalid driver's license	Sorter	0	1	1	Full-time	Not Applic	Unspecifie	Events Ser	Other		
16	Account Exec	AU, NSW, Sales				Adhena is the UK	Are you into Youa	"I'll need in return"	0	1	0	Full-time	Associate	Bachelor's	Internet	Sales		
17	VP of Sales	US, FL, S. Sales				120000-150000	Salary	Minimum is about 100k	Very Superior Basic	SSG	0	1	1	Full-time	Executive	Bachelor's	Facilities	Sales
18	Hands-On	US, TX, A. RD				At Home/Book	vs We are too	Previous experience in cl	0	1	0	Full-time	Mid-senior level	Internet	Engineerin			
19	Southend-on	GB, SCS, Southend-on-Sea				Established on	the Governor 16-18 year old	Career pr	0	1	1							
20	Visual Desig	US, NY, New York				Kettle is an indep	Kettle is hiring a Visual Designer	Job	0	1	0							
21	Process Con	US, PA, USA, Northeast				We Provide Full	T Experience: Must have 5 or more	ye	0	0	0	Full-time						
22	Marketing A	US, TX, Austin				IntelliBright was	c IntelliBright Job Requirements	assist i	0	1	0							
23	Front End	DE, NZ, N, Auckland				Frustrated with th'	Want to Be You will most I	You will b	0	1	0	Full-time	Mid-Senior Master's	C Consumer	Engineerin			
24	Engagement	AE,, Engagement				Upstream™ m	the positio Requirements	Salary & a	0	1	1	Full-time	Mid-Senior Bachelor's	Telecomm	Sales			
25	Vice Preside	US, CA, C. Business/Fin	100000-120000			WOM Group is an	HR, cld Job Requirement	Business/fin	0	1	0	Full-time	Executive	Unspecifie	Internet	Sales		
26	Customer Sr	GB, LND, London				We are a canary	what based e-com		0	0	0							
27	H1B SPOUS	US, NY, New York				I2B Technologies	Hello! Wish JAVA, .NET, SQL, ORACLE		0	1	1							
28	Marketing E	SG,, Marketing				If working in a	call We are cur	this position is We are lc	0	1	0	Full-time	Associate	Online Me	Marketing			
29	HAAD/DHA	AE, AZ, AI/Medical				We the Medical R	HAAD/DHA Requirements	Our client	0	1	0	Full-time	Associate	Master's	D Hospital & Health Car			

B. Data Analysis

Data analysis must be done after data collection in order to gain understanding about the data under consideration. We can acquire a visual understanding of the distribution of the data with the help of python modules and libraries like pandas, numpy, matplotlib, and seaborn. These tools also provide us a clear understanding about the difference between real and fake jobs. We can see from the analysis stage how filthy our data is and how much data cleaning is necessary.

C. Data Cleaning and Pre-processing

Preprocessing involves converting unclean data into a clean data collection. The dataset is preprocessed to look for missing values, noisy data, and other anomalies before the algorithm is performed. Stop words, unnecessary characteristics, and extra space are also removed from the text, along with noise and uninformative letters and phrases. The data set needs to be pre-processed due to its nature before being given into the classifier. Figure 2 shows the columns in dataset with null values

Fig.2

job_id	0
title	0
location	346
department	11547
salary_range	15012
company_profile	3308
description	1
requirements	2695
benefits	7210
telecommuting	0
has_company_logo	0
has_questions	0
employment_type	3471
required_experience	7050
required_education	8105
industry	4903
function	6455
fraudulent	0
dtype: int64	

D. Splitting dataset into Train and Test data

Each machine learning model will have the data split into two distinct sets: the training set and the test set. In this instance, the algorithm model will use the information in the data to produce predictions. Generally, we separate the data set into ratios of 70:30 or 80:20. 30% of the data were collected for the test, while 70% were taken for the train. The Splitting, however, may change according on the shape and size of the dataset.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The data preparation and training are both essential processes in the machine learning pipeline. Adaptive

machine learning models differ from non-adaptive machine learning models in that they can generalize to previously unexplored data. By using a variety of performance evaluation metrics, we should be able to improve our model's overall predictive capacity before deploying it for production on untested data. Without performing a thorough analysis of the ML model using a variety of metrics and relying solely on accuracy, it may cause issues when the related model is applied to unknowable data, leading to inaccurate predictions. Figure 5 shows the features analysis.

Fig.5

To gain a basic understanding of the correctness and effectiveness of the various models utilized, classification reports for all the used models are printed. The classification reports of the various algorithms are displayed in Figures 6 and 7.

Fig.6 – Classification Result of SVM Algorithm

	precision	recall	f1-score	support
0	0.83	0.89	0.86	236
1	0.90	0.85	0.87	284
accuracy			0.87	520
macro avg	0.86	0.87	0.86	520
weighted avg	0.87	0.87	0.87	520

Fig.7 – Classification Result of Random Forest

	precision	recall	f1-score	support
0	0.83	0.93	0.88	236
1	0.94	0.84	0.88	284
accuracy			0.88	520
macro avg	0.88	0.89	0.88	520
weighted avg	0.89	0.88	0.88	520

VI. CONCLUSION

The detection of job scams has recently become a major problem worldwide. In this Research, we conducted an experiment using a job dataset that includes both actual and false job postings. We tested Support Vector Machine and Random Forest in this work. The outcome displays a comparison between accuracy of Support Vector Machine and Random.

Random Forest had the best classification accuracy, at 88%, and Support Vector Machine had the second-highest accuracy, at 86%.

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